

METHODS OF FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN LESSONS OF LANGUAGE FOR YOUNG SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Annotation: Communicative presupposes the possession of all types of speech activity, the construction of productive speech interaction with peers and adults; adequate perception of oral and written speech, accurate, correct, logical and expressive presentation of one's point of view on the problem posed, observance in the process of communication of the basic norms of oral and written speech and the rules of Uzbek speech etiquette.

Key words: competence, ability to learn, analysis of objects, synthesis, derivation of consequences, establishment, construction of a logical chain, proof, hypotheses and their substantiation, statement and solution of the problem, formulation of the problem, independent creation.

Education in the Uzbek language lessons should be built taking into account the need to develop students' various communication skills and abilities:

- the ability to understand the topic of the message, the logic of the development of thought,
- extract the necessary information (in whole or in part),
- penetrate into the meaning of the statement - listening;
- learning reading skills;
- the skills of conducting a dialogue and constructing a monologue statement - speaking;
- skills, comprehending the topic and the main idea (idea) of the statement,

Collect and organize material

- make a plan, use different types of speech,
- construct a statement in a certain style,
- selection of language
- improve the statement - writing, speaking [11, 241],

The effectiveness of Uzbek language lessons is directly dependent on how rationally organized the change of oral and written tasks is, how the relationship between oral and written speech of students is thought out, whether conditions are created for students to overcome the difficulties that arise in the transition from thought to speech, from speech to thought.

The most effective is comprehensive speech training, in which the ability to perceive oral and written speech (listening and reading) is formed in combination with the ability to build oral and written statements (speaking and writing). In each type of speech activity, in addition to specific skills and abilities, skills are formed that are common to all types of activity [8].

Speech activity, as a creative activity, according to numerous studies, is a multi-tiered mechanism, the essence of which follows from the characteristics of human activity. Any human activity, in turn, is characterized by structure, that is, it consists of a certain sequence

of actions that are organized in such a way as to achieve a certain goal with the least amount of time. "In order to fully communicate," writes A.A. Leontiev, "a person must, in principle, have a number of skills. He must, firstly, be able to quickly and correctly navigate in communication conditions, and secondly, be able to plan his speech correctly, correctly to choose the content of the act of communication, thirdly, to find adequate means for conveying this content, and fourthly, to be able to provide feedback. If any of the links in the act of communication is violated, then the speaker will not be able to achieve the expected results of communication - it will be ineffective " .

A special place in the development of students' speech belongs to the work with the text. There are a large number of types of text analysis in the Uzbek language lesson: cultural, literary, linguistic, linguo-semantic and complex.

Forms for working with text:

syntactic five-minute;

· turn on imagination;

Write like this

through an additional task to the dictation;

· compiling a table [7, 241].

Improving the speech activity of students, the teacher relies on the most diverse types and genres of statements on literary topics, which, when teaching, create conditions for the versatile speech and aesthetic development of the student's personality. He has the ability to select these genres based on the following classification of coherent monologues [7, 241]. :

. Scientific, literary: detailed oral answer, message, report.

. Literary-critical: literary review, critical study, critical essay, "word about the writer", etc.

. Art criticism: a story or report about a work of art (a painting, sculpture, architectural structure), a guide's speech, a director's commentary, etc.

. Publicistic: speech about the hero of the work, oratory, reportage, etc.

. Artistic and creative:

a) literary and artistic - poems, stories, essays, plays, etc., independently composed by schoolchildren;

b) artistic and critical: artistic and biographical story, story about a literary event, artistic sketch, etc.

Thus, we can say that the subject of the Uzbek language plays a leading role in the formation of communicative universal educational activities. [7, 241]

The main indicators of functional literacy are communicative, cognitive, regulatory universal learning activities.

Communicative UUD presupposes the possession of all types of speech activity, the construction of productive speech interaction with peers and adults; adequate perception of oral and written speech, accurate, correct, logical and expressive presentation of one's point of view on the problem posed, observance in the process of communication of the basic norms of oral and written speech and the rules of Uzbek speech etiquette.

Content that ensures the formation of communicative competence:

. Speech and verbal communication.

Speech is oral and written, monologue (narration, description, reasoning, a combination of types of monologue) and dialogic.

. Speech activity.

Types of speech activity: reading, listening (listening), speaking, writing. Understanding text information, conveying content. Presentation of the content of the listened or read text (detailed, concise, selective). Creation of oral and written monologic and dialogic statements of different communicative orientation.

. Text.

Text as a speech product. Theme, micro-theme. Types of text processing (plan, synopsis, abstract). Text analysis.

. Functional varieties of language.

Speech styles, sphere of use, style genres.

· The formation of communicative universal educational activities is an integral part of language education at school.

· Language competence implies knowledge of the language itself, its structure and functioning, language norms, including spelling and punctuation.

It is the language and communicative competencies that contribute to the formation of the skills and abilities of verbal communication. And for this it is necessary to create conditions for verbal communication at each lesson. Speech activity is formed in all its forms - reading, speaking, writing, listening. "To teach communication by communicating" - without these conditions there is no lesson.

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